

REVIEW: *THE SECRET TALE OF TESUR HOUSE* BY BRAG GDONG BKRAS GLING DBANG RDOR

བྲག་གཏོང་བཀྲ་ས་གླིང་དབང་རྡོར།

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Brag gdong bkras gling dbang rdor བྲག་གཏོང་བཀྲ་ས་གླིང་དབང་རྡོར། 2011. *Bkras zur tshang gi gsang ba'i gtam rgyud* བཀྲ་ས་ལུང་ཚང་གི་གསང་བའི་གཏམ་རྒྱུད། [*The Secret Tale of Bkras zur House*]. Lha sa ལྷ་ས།: Bod ljong mi dmang dpe bskrun khang བོད་ལྗོངས་མི་དམངས་དཔེ་སྐྱུག་ཁང། [Tibet People's Publishing House]. 297 pp. ISBN 978-7-223-010064-1 (Paperback 22RMB).

Wangdor Tailing [Brag gdong bkras gling dbang rdor བྲག་གཏོང་བཀྲ་ས་གླིང་དབང་རྡོར།]. 1998. *The Secret Tale of Tesur House* [*Bkras zur tshang gi gsang ba'i gtam rgyud* བཀྲ་ས་ལུང་ཚང་གི་གསང་བའི་གཏམ་རྒྱུད།]. Beijing 北京: Zhongguo zangxue chubanshe 中国藏学出版社 [China Tibetology Publishing House]. 351 pp. ISBN 7-80057361-3. (Paperback, 2.99USD).¹

Wangduo 旺多 (Suolang Wangqing 索朗旺清 [Bsod nams dbang chen བསོད་ནམས་དབང་ཚེས།], translator). 1998. *Zhaisufu miwen* 斋苏府秘闻 [*The Secret Tale of Tesur House*]. Beijing 北京: Zhongguo zangxue chubanshe 中国藏学出版社 [China Tibetology Publishing House]. 216 pp. ISBN 7-80057-362-1 (paperback 12RMB).

The Tibetan and English versions of *The Secret Tale of Bkras zur House* introduce Brag gdong bkras gling dbang rdor. Born in 1934 in the noble Brag gdong bkras gling family in the Rgal rtse (Jiangze) area, he began traditional schooling in Lha sa.² In 1946, he attended St. Joseph's College in Darjeeling, India. In early 1953, he returned to Tibet as a teacher and officer in the Rgyal rtse and Gzhis ka rtse (Rika ze) areas.

In 1977, he worked at the Tibet Education Bureau in Lha sa. Eight years later, with the growing tourism industry in Tibet, he joined the Tibet Tourism Bureau and made business trips to the USA, Canada, Nepal, Bolivia, and Hong Kong. From 1986 to 1987, he worked for China Tibet Qomolangma [Jo mo gling ma] Travelways in Hongkong.³

After retirement in 1992, he began work on literary creations and translations, including *Hamlet*⁴ and *Romeo and Juliet*⁵ from English to Tibetan, *Tibet: The Land and the People*⁶ from

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¹ Amazon price (<https://amzn.to/3gsgIUT>, accessed 4 August 2020).

² See Cao and Yan (2009) for more on the author's childhood in Tibet, return to China from India, writings, and health.

³ <https://bit.ly/3itYYJ6>, accessed 12 August 2020.

⁴ William Shakespeare and Bkras gling dbang rdor. 2002. *Ham lekri*. Lha sa: Bod ljongs mi dmangs dpe skrun khang.

⁵ William Shakespeare and Bkras gling dbang rdor. 2003. *Ro me'o dang ju likri*. Lha sa: Bod ljongs mi dmangs dpe skrun khang.

⁶ Tildy Chodag and Bkras gling dbang rdor. 1988. *Tibet, the Land and the People*. Beijing: New World Press. <https://tinyurl.com/yyybcdka> (accessed 14 January 2021).

Chinese to English, and *The Drama Songs of Tshangs dbyang rgya mtsho*¹ from Tibetan to English. He authored *A Tour Guide's Diary* in English and *The Secret Tale of Tesur House* in Tibetan and English.

According to the writer's acknowledgment in the Tibetan and English versions, the Tibetan version of *The Secret Tale of Tesur House* was originally written in 1993 and began to be serially published in *Tibetan Literature and Art* a year later. In 2003, the Tibetan version was broadcast by the Tibetan Department, China National Radio (CNR). The novel was translated into Chinese by Bsod nambs dbang chen and, in 1996, was published in *Tibetan Literature*. The novel won the 1997 Rlung rta Cup, 1999 Tibetan New Times, 2001 Jo mo glang ma, and 2005 Gangs rgyan rtags ma awards. In 1995, the author completed an English version. A German version (*Das Geheimnis des Hauses Tesur*) was published in 2001, and the author mentions that he had received requests to translate *The Secret Tale of Tesur House* into Korean and Japanese.

The Secret Tale of Tesur House primarily uses the first person point of view, supplemented by the occasional use of the third person (Lcags rdor rgyal 2019:322). 'Brug rgyas, the main narrator, was born in a poor family and lived on farmland rented from the aristocratic Bkras rab pa family. Rent was paid by a family member annually by working for the landlord during harvest time.

The story begins with 'Brug rgyas on his way to Lha sa as a mule driver. Among several corpses he found at the Rdza ra postal station, 'Brug rgyas notices an injured man, who he puts on one of his mules and continues to the Srin lag postal station. Once they arrive, a woman whose family runs the postal station attempts to smother the injured man. When she sees 'Brug rgyas approaching, she runs at him, holding a knife in her right hand. 'Brug rgyas aims at the woman's right hand with his gun but accidentally shoots and kills her.

The story examines the narrator from his childhood to his business career to answer mysterious questions surrounding the conflict between the woman at the Srin lag postal station and the injured man.

Elder Master, the injured man, was the narrator's childhood friend and the landlord's son, who lived in Lha sa City. His noble parents opposed his wish to marry a beautiful commoner who served his family. Instead, they arranged marriage to a noblewoman. A disagreement ensued, culminating in Elder Master running away on the night of his wedding and selling his valuables to procure a horse with a plan of going to India to sell wool collected from Tibetan areas and importing goods from India.

Later, on a wool-collection trip, Elder Master stopped at the Rdza ra postal station that also functioned as an inn. Three people attacked him, and though rendered unconscious, he survived. This was the situation when 'Brug rgyas encountered Elder Master, whom he then took to the next postal station. Because of the woman's death, the two travelers were put in Sna skar rtse Prison. Later, they learned that the dead woman's husband was involved in the Rdza ra event and killed.

Meanwhile, Elder Master received medical treatment in a prison official's home. After recovering, he was sent back to prison. Later, the prisoners were released, thanks to negotiations between Sna dkar rtse authorities and Elder Master's father.

Elder Master next searched for the woman he wanted to marry. Expelled from his father's estate, he found her living in the mountains near Lha sa City with an old nun. Elder Master's family gave a small amount of property to the new couple to fulfill the young lovers' desire to marry, which allowed Elder Master to develop his wool business. Over time, he sent wool to India and imported matches, soap, rice, oil, fruit, and candy to Lha sa City, where his wife, A cag mtsho rgyal, ran a small shop.

¹ Tshangs dbyangs rgya mtsho and Bkras gling dbang rdor. 2009. *Love Songs of Tsangyang Gyatso*. Varanasi: Pilgrims Publ.

In the novel's second part, the daughter of the woman 'Brug rgyas accidentally killed at the Srin lag postal station became homeless. While on the way to India, 'Brug rgyas noticed her living on Sna dkar rtse County Town's streets. Feeling guilty, he took her to Elder Master's home, where the couple decided to adopt her and named her Pad+ma.

After enrolling her in a private school, some noble parents learned of a blacksmith in Pad+ma's background, which relegated her to a low social class. Consequently, she had to leave the private school for nobles. Elder Master then decided to enroll Pad+ma in a British boarding school for girls in India. Later, while staying in a classmate's home in England, Pad+ma learned about the family's sheep wool company, whose wool mainly was from Tibet but imported from India. With Pad+ma's help, Elder Master signed a contract with the English family. This new business relationship was instrumental in Elder Master's family becoming wealthier and becoming known as the Bkras zur House, which monopolized sheep wool in Tibet.

The Bkras zur Family plans to build their wool company in Lha sa City and improve Tibetans' economy and life conditions. However, their proposal was rejected by the Tibet government. Later, Elder Master commented to Pad+ma:

At the beginning of this century cars and hydraulic electricity were said to have been introduced but soon were forbidden or stopped out of carelessness. As I remember the Bengali hairstyle and football even were forbidden (English version:301).

Conservative officials interpreted modernity as the beginning of a period of degeneration, so they opposed new things and challenges that might destroy their old life patterns. Continuing their comfort was the priority. Moreover, officials did not construct roads, bridges, and companies to improve people's daily lives. Elder Master explained to Pad+ma:

The yearly round duty of the government offices is merely settling the balance of account between the yearly income and expenditure, and most of the time of the officials is spent on festivals and entertainment (English version:300).

'Brug rgyas and Pad+ma grew closer over the years and eventually loved each other passionately. However, on their wedding night, Pad+ma's uncle had just been released from prison for stealing. Seeking revenge for his relatives killed at the Rdza ra and Srin lag postal stations by Elder Master and 'Brug rgyas, he killed Elder Master. This threw A cag mtsho rgyal into such agony that she killed herself the same night. The next night, the killer tried to kill 'Brug rgyas with a knife, but accidentally killed Pad+ma before 'Brug rgyas shot and killed him.

'Brug rgyas, the narrator, fled from Bkras zur House and lived as a monk in a mountain cave while writing this story and then committed suicide in the Skyid chu [Lha sa River] leaving only Elder Master's little son, and 'Brug rgyas' sister and her husband.

As the author notes, death begins and ends the novel, as does escape, forming a mandala of samsara. As Caibei notes, "It's like making a Buddhist mandala, which is drawn carefully and completely by monks, who then slowly wipe the picturesque mandala away with their hands." Caibei adds, "Artists, perhaps, appreciate only the process of creating art, like this novel, the author puts all his characters on the stage for a while until, in the end, they all vanish into death" (2009:73).

In this novel, the mandala of life mirrors Tibetan society in the 1940s, especially the Lha sa high class' life, including various rituals, beliefs, morals, customs, ways of dressing, food, and relationships and conflicts between social classes. Humor, symbols, the historical background of places, and detailed descriptions of characters add to the novel's value.

As Cabezón notes, "Not only does ritual fill Tibetan space, but it also pervades Tibetan time" (2009:introduction, 3). This novel is embedded with numerous rituals, including the narrator's wedding. On the wedding night, attendants escort the bride and bridegroom to their bed in the nuptial chamber, undress them completely, and offer a *gro so phye mar* 'wooden vessel of flour used in New Year ceremonies and weddings' and liquor to the new couple to sprinkle to encourage auspiciousness. Additionally, barley grains roughly placed to resemble a swastika¹ have been placed under the couple's sheet for later inspection. If the barley is scattered, it signals the couple had sexual intercourse, pleasing the family. After the killings on the same night, death rituals are also held in Bkras zur House.

Featured customary practices include the narrator's mother offering tea, liquor, a white silk scarf, and prayers for the safety of 'Brug rgyas as he leaves home for Lha sa. Auspicious dates are also important, e.g., when Pad+ma was expelled from the private school in Lha sa and sent to India for further education, a propitious date was selected, and offerings were made of a white silk scarf and *gro 'bras* 'a bowl or plate of rice with wild yams, ghee, and sugar'.

Symbols and signs include doors decorated with swastikas and drawings of scorpions² in Ra lung. In prison, the narrator noticed marks on walls made by prisoners to count dates and the passage of time. For example, the narrator drew a pig on a wall to represent the Year of the Pig and scratched eleven marks plus two additional marks to represent the month and date. Similarly, before Pad+ma attended the private school, Pad+ma and A cag mtsho rgyal drew the shapes of goods and used marks to count how many things they sold and the amount of money they earned.

Two maps and descriptions of customs and rituals enhance the story's authenticity, making "the story artfully and culturally special and complete" (Bse chang sha bo tshe brtan 2019:169). Lcags rdor rgyal adds that "the two maps ... purposely include all possible spaces in the whole narrative... clarifying the narration and showing the importance of space in the novel" (2019:349).

An article written by the author states that he illustrated all the corrupt activities of the Tibetan noble class listed in the novel, as his editor suggested.³ The novel's portrayal of the Tibetan aristocratic class' dark elements and its dysfunction employs a series of events to expose corruption, conflicts between leaders, and general government dysfunction. The government, for example, seems unaware of assassinations and robberies at postal stations. When the narrator and Elder Master were imprisoned in Sna dkar County, local officials hid evidence of the Rdza ra event. Fortunately, the family Elder Master stayed with recovering from his injuries, secretly informed his father of his predicament. Holding an important position in Lha sa City, he could extricate 'Brug rgyas and his son from prison.

After Elder Master grew wealthy through dealings with the UK's wool company, the narrator encouraged him to start a company in Tibet. However, the government rejected Elder Master's application on the grounds that introducing machines was unacceptable because it would harm Buddha's noble dharma in Tibetan areas.

A song spread among Tibetans circumambulating the Jo khang Temple and at bars in Lha sa City:

Terab [Bkras rab] sacrificed five thousand,
And went into a deep slumber,
Samphel [Bsam' phe] sacrificed ten thousand,
And took him by surprise (English version:287).

¹ Symbolizing the footprints or feet of the Buddha in the Buddhist tradition.

² See Beer (2003) for multiple, complex meanings associated with the scorpion. Also see <https://bit.ly/2ZxmsGq> (accessed 12 September 2020).

³ <https://bit.ly/2UDbb5B>, accessed 10 January 2020.

These lines describe the conflict between Bkras rab, Elder Master's father, and Bsam's phel, competing for a government position. The latter was aware of 5,000 silver coins Bkras rab had given the Regent. Bsam 'phel then secretly gave 10,000 silver coins to ensure that he was appointed to this coveted position and hired beggars and itinerant singers to sing and spread rumors that the new minister was none other than Lord Bkras rab, which reassured him and explains Bkras rab's surprise when he was not appointed.

Despite the exposure of the Tibetan high class' shortcomings, positive social aspects are also provided. Without restriction on crossing the Tibet border on business, Pad+ma and Elder Master went to India on business and for better education, respectively. Descriptions of mule drivers passing over the border imply robust cross-border movement of businessmen and travelers.

A strict social hierarchy did not prevent those born in the bottom social class from moving up if they became educated or otherwise developed their abilities. For example, Pad+ma's classmates discriminated against her because of her low social class background. However, after graduating from a school in India, noble young Tibetan men wrote her love letters.

Furthermore, not all high-class nobles were cruel and selfish. Elder Master, a young nobleman representative of the high-class, is depicted positively as a man full of sympathy for others. He believed in equality; married a commoner; made friends with commoners, including slaves; adopted an orphan, Pad+ma, who was from a very low social position according to Lha sa standards; and was concerned about the Tibetan nation and its future, not only about his career.

Caibei writes that an outstanding theme is how aristocracy and slavery melded to be the modern Tibetan intellectual figure at the end of the novel (2009:73), providing a good model for young Tibetans to use their ability to develop and make progress. Virtanen (2016:500) comments that "What is special is that they [the main four characters] are depicted as deciding to form one family and to cooperate and help each other on equal terms."

In terms of language, the Tibetan version features various colloquial terms and phrases used in the Lha sa dialect that I found challenging, including, among others, such terms as *skya* (Literary Tibetan (LT): *gyang*¹) 'wall' and *sing stong* (LT: *sna tha*) 'snuff'. Fodder is of two types. *Thor rtswa* 'dawn fodder' is given to animals at dawn, and *'job rtswa* 'milking fodder' is given to female yaks and cows when they are being milked. Other phrases I was unfamiliar with include *khyi' dogs sar pel pel dang me mda' 'gel sar ang gses*, a parable from a Tibetan folktale suggesting 'to set things opposite to [one's] hosts' arrangement as in a Tibetan folktale."²

The author also borrowed English terms like "good morning," "pocket," "jeans," "railway," and "beer" with footnoted explanations. While "piano" is *rno sbreng* in Tibetan, the author or his editor employs the Chinese term *gangqin* and gave the English "piano" (Tibetan version:195).

While I applaud the Chinese and English language versions, they do not represent the diversity and characteristics of colloquial language expressed so well in the Tibetan version. As a native of Amdo, I was stumped by certain colloquial terms used in the Chinese and English versions that offered explanations of colloquial terms, such as the folktale mentioned above, that is given in full in the English version. It reminded me of what I had heard, with some slight differences, in my childhood. Ritual descriptions, conversations, proverbs, and local terms in the Chinese and English versions lack some of the colloquial Tibetan version's rich flavors.

¹ Literary Tibetan.

² A folktale provided as a footnote in the English version (92) describes a thief boasting of his skill at stealing. When he tells a rich man that he can rob him the latter says it is impossible, so they make a bet. At night, the thief quietly ties a calf where the rich man usually ties his dog and hangs a stick where the rich man usually hangs his gun. During the robbery, the rich man tries to let loose his dog, but finds it is a calf. He then runs for his gun, but discovers it is a stick, so the robbery is successful and the rich man loses the wager.

Humorous moments include Elder Master's younger brother replacing Elder Master after the latter escapes from his home on his wedding night. The next morning, the barley grains forming a swastika under the bedsheet are scattered, and the couple then lives together.

Another humorous moment is during the time 'Brug rgyas and Pad+ma are in love, the latter hands a love letter to the narrator. Illiterate,¹ 'Brug rgyas, repeatedly gazes at the piece of paper while at home. His mother is amazed by her son's ability and asks him to read it to her. He then chants memorized daily religious recitations while moving a finger from line to line of the letter. Comparing this humorous description in the Tibetan, Chinese, and English language versions, readers can better appreciate the translation challenges.

The English and Chinese versions of this work offer many cultural notes. For example, traditional hats, shoes, and clothing are explained. Names for animals and people are also translated in pages at the end of the book. Religious ceremonies mentioned in the story are also clarified at the end of the English version. Such notes may help cultural outsiders. However, as for A mdo readers, like me, unfamiliar with Lha sa colloquial terms and daily customs, I suggest reading the Tibetan, Chinese, and English language versions.

While this story provides historical comments on Tibetan society in the 1940s, certain aspects seem to contradict actual contemporary mainstream Tibetan life. For example, the orphan, Pad+ma, was later adopted by Elder Master (her father's killer), eventually married 'Brug rgyas (Pad+ma's mother's killer), and was easily persuaded that her parents were evil killers and robbers in Sna dkar rtse. Bse chang sha bo tshe brtan (2013:173) commented that this description is unconvincing. Orthofer also comments critically:

A few events are very casually and quickly handled – in particular the transformation of Pema, who is able to leave her trauma behind her without much of a second thought (never mind [sic] the psychological issues surrounding her falling in love with the man who is responsible for mom's death ...).²

Why did the author create such a plot? First, the author emphasizes Pad+ma's justiciable nature that might have been strengthened by religious context. When 'Brug rgyas accidentally shot and killed Pad+ma's mother, he was not worried about being judged but about being a killer. Second, the author may want readers to experience the unpredictable. He mentioned that he modeled some of the novel's content after watching several Indian movies.³

Lama Jabb (2005) argues that oral and traditional literary forms powerfully influence modern Tibetan-language literature, which is evident in the novel under review. Unit five of the first part is titled 'Sending a Sheep', with "sheep" signaling a wealthy traveler who is easily robbed.⁴ The author has further commented on this, describing how, in his childhood, he heard stories of innkeepers conspiring to rob rich travelers ("sheep") (see footnote 11).

This novel attracts Tibetan readers; for example, some of my A mdo friends have read and recommended it, and during my several readings in three languages, I laughed and forgot the time.

¹ Later, the narrator learned reading and writing in Tibetan with Pad+ma's help.

² <https://bit.ly/3clGgBS>, accessed 4 August 2020.

³ <https://bit.ly/3iNBaAv>, accessed 25 August 2020.

⁴ Myang tsha dkar rgyan sent a coded message via a beggar to her son Mi la ras pa (1028/40–1111/23), the great Tibetan yo gi. See Rus pa'i rgyan (2004:43-45) for more.

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TIBETAN TERMS

'job rtswa འཛོལ་རྩུ།

a mdo ཨ་མདོ།

bkras rab བཀྲས་རབ།

bsam 'phel བསམ་འཕེལ།

bse chang sha bo tshe brtan བསེ་ཚང་ཤ་བོ་ཚེ་བརྟན།

bsod nams dbang chen བསོད་ནམས་དབང་ཚེན།

gangs rgyan rtags ma གངས་རྒྱན་རྟགས་མ།

gro 'bras གྲོ་འབྲས།

gro so phye mar གྲོ་སོ་ཕྱེ་མར།

gyang གྱང།

gzhis ka rtse གཞིས་ཀ་རེུ།

jo khang རྫོང་ཁང།

jo mo gling ma རྫོམོ་གླིང་མ།

khyi 'dogs sar pel pel me mda' 'gel sar ang gses ཁྱི་འདོགས་སར་ཤེལ་ཤེལ་མེ་མདའ་ཀེལ་སར་ཨང་གསེས།

lcags rdor rgyal ལུགས་རྡོར་རྒྱལ།

lha sa ལྷ་ས།

myang tsha dkar rgyan མྱང་ཚ་དཀར་རྒྱལ།

mi la ras pa མི་ལ་རས་པ།

pad+ma rig 'dzin པད་མ་རིག་འཛིན།

rgyal rtse རྒྱལ་རེུ།

rlung rta རླུང་རྟ།

rno sbreng རྩོལ་སྤྲོད།

tshe dbal ཚེ་དཔལ།

sing stong སིང་སྟོང།

skya སྐྱ།

skyid chu སྐྱིད་ཚུ།

sna dkar སྤྲ་དཀར།

sna tha སྤྲ་ཐ།

thor rtswa ཐོར་རྩུ།

tshangs dbyang rgya mtsho ཚངས་དབྱངས་རྒྱ་མཚོ།

CHINESE TERMS

Caibei 才贝

gangqin 钢琴

Jiangze 江孜